

ASIANELLUS FESTIVUS (C.L. KOCH, 1834) (ARANEAE: SALTICIDAE) THE FIRST RECORD FROM SERBIA

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Logunov & Hęciak (1996) erected the genus *Asianellus* Logunov et Hęciak, 1996 (Araneae: Salticidae: Aelurillinae) to accommodate the congeners of the *festivus* species group of *Aelurillus* 1884. According to the World Spider Catalog (2018), *Asianellus* currently consists of five valid species, of which only one has been known from Europe viz. *Asianellus festivus* (C.L. Koch, 1834). However, until now, this species has not been found in Serbia. In this paper, I report on *A. festivus* from the fauna of Serbia for the first time.

This paper is based on material collected by the author in the vicinity of Jagodina (Central Serbia). Specimens were hand-collected and stored in 70% alcohol. Identification was made by means of a Meopta binocular microscope and BTC Stm 2B stereomicroscope. The species was identified by the conformation of its copulatory organs, as illustrated by Harm (1977), Prószyński (1982), Logunov & Hęciak (1996), Zabka (1997) and Metzner (1999). The studied specimens were photographed using a Fujifilm AX650 camera attached to the stereomicroscope. The nomenclature follows World Spider Catalog (2018).

Asianellus Logunov et Hęciak, 1996

Asianellus festivus (C.L. Koch, 1834) (Fig. 1)

Euophrys festiva C. L. Koch, 1834: 123, f. 5-6 (D).

Phlegra festiva: Harm, 1977: 69, f. 2a-b, 10-12, 14a-b (Tmf from *Aelurillus*, rejected).

Aelurillus festivus: Prószyński, 1982: 274, f. 1, 3, 7, 9 (mf).

Asianellus festivus: Logunov & Hęciak, 1996: 106, f. 1-5, 8, 10, 17-19, 23-28, 39 (Tmf from *Phlegra*, S).

Asianellus festivus: Zabka, 1997: 38, f. 47-53 (mf).

Asianellus festivus: Metzner, 1999: 71, f. 36a-l (mf).

For a complete set of taxonomic references see World Spider Catalog (2018).

Figure 1. *Asianellus festivus*. A, B, D – female, dorsal, ventral and frontal view, C, E – male, dorsal and frontal view, F, G – epigyne, H, I – male, pedipalp, ventral and lateral view. (Photo by B. Stanković).

Material examined: Jagodina: Bresje, 1 ♀ (43°56'16.0"N 21°15'37.8"E; 130 m a.s.l.), moderately wet grassland, 23.04.2016, 1 ♀ 12.05.2016, leg. det. B. Stanković; Jagodina: Leštar, 1 ♂ (43°56'35.9"N 21°16'39.6"E; 132 m a.s.l.), ruderal habitat, on the ground, 02.06.2017, leg. & det. B. Stanković.

Remarks: The structures of the copulatory organs undoubtedly indicate that the studied specimens belong to *A. festivus*. The epigyne (Fig. 1: F, G) bears sclerotized copulatory openings and the epigynal pocket. The male palp (Fig. 1: H, I) has tibial apophysis with two unequally long processes and a thin, coiled embolus. The visible embolic part is situated at the distal end of the bulbus (cf. Metzner, 2018; Nentwig *et al.*, 2018).

Body lengths of the collected specimens: male 6 mm, females 7.8 and 8.0 mm. According to the literature data (Logunov & Hęciak, 1996), the male body length can reach 6-7 mm, that of females 6.5-8.5 mm. However, Nentwig *et al.*, (2018) gave the following ranges of the species' body length: males 5.95-8 mm, females 8.0 mm.

Phenology: According to the online data of the Czech Arachnological Society (2018), adults of both sexes are active from March to November, being mostly active in May-September. However, based on the online information provided by "Arachnologische Gesellschaft" (2018), males are active in March-September, and females in March-August.

Global distribution: A trans-Eurasian temperate species (Logunov & Hęciak, 1996).

Habitats: *A. festivus* occurs in dry, mostly sunny spots, often preferring rocky terrains (Braun, 1957; Buchar, 1960; Broen, 1963; Harm, 1977). Heimer & Nentwig (1984) showed that the species can occur in bogs; also, according to Nentwig *et al.* (2018), it can occur in warm, sunny rock fields, slopes and in grass or on land dominated by mosses or lichens, dry grasslands, habitats with very sparse or no vegetation (Arachnologische Gesellschaft, 2018).

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References: Arachnologische Gesellschaft (2018). Atlas of the European Arachnids. Online at <https://atlas.arages.de> [Accessed on: 12.12.2018], SW Version 1.38.2. Braun, R. (1957). *Jahrbücher des Nassauischen Vereins für Naturkunde*, Wiesbaden, 93, 21-95. Broen, B. von (1963). *Mitteilungen der Deutschen Entomologischen Gesellschaft*, Berlin, 22(4), 68-74. Buchar, J. (1960). *Acta Universitatis Carolinae - Biologica*, 2, 87-102. Czech Arachnological Society, (2018). Distribution Maps of Arachnids in Czechia. Online at www.arachnology.cz [Accessed on: 12.12.2018]. Harm, M. (1977). *Senckenbergiana biologica*, 58 (1/2), 63-77. Heimer, S. & Nentwig, W. (1984). *Faunistische Abhandlungen Staatliches Museum für Tierkunde*, 12(4), 45-51. Koch, C. L. (1834). *Arachniden*, 122-127. In: Herrich-Schäffer, G. A. W. (Eds.). *Deutschlands Insecten*. 34. F. Pustet, Regensburg. 190 pp. Logunov, D.V. (1992). *Arthropoda Selecta*, 1(2), 47-71. Logunov, D.V. & Hęciak S. (1996). *Entomologica Scandinavica*, 26, 103-117. Metzner, H. (1999). *Andrias*, 14, 1-279. Metzner, H. (2018). Jumping spiders (Arachnida: Araneae: Salticidae) of the world. Online at <https://www.jumping-spiders.com> [Accessed on: 13 December 2018]. Nentwig, W., Blick, T., Gloor, D., Hänggi, A. & Kropf, C. (2018). Spiders of Europe. Version 12.2018. Online at <https://www.araneae.nmbe.ch> [Accessed on: 12.12.2018]. Prószyński, J. (1982). *Annales Historico-Naturales Musei Nationalis Hungarici*, 74, 273-294. World Spider Catalog (2018). World Spider Catalog. Version 19.5. Natural History Museum Bern. Online at <http://wsc.nmbe.ch> [Accessed on: 12.12.2018]. Zabka, M. (1997). *Fauna Polski (Fauna Poloniae)*, 19, 1-188.

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ПРВИ НАЛАЗ У СРБИЈИ

БОБАН СТАНКОВИЋ

ИЗВОД

Asianellus festivus (C. L. Koch, 1834) је нова врста паука скакача за фауну Србије. Забележена је на локалитетима Бресје и Лештар у околини Јагодине. Дати су подаци о биологији и екологији врсте, фотографије хабитуса мужјака и женке и цртежи копулаторних органа.

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